

Supporting information

Sb₂Se₃ Thin Film Growth from Solution Atomic Layer Deposition

Vanessa M. Koch,^{*,2} Jaroslav Charvot,^{*,1,2} Yuanyuan Cao,² Claudia Hartmann,³

Regan G. Wilks,³ Ivan Kunderata,^{2,4} Ignacio Mínguez-Bacho,² Negar Gheshlaghi,²

(Tobias?),^{5,6} Wiebke Alex,⁷ Daniel Pokorný,¹ Ece Tupraksal,⁸ Ana S. Smith,⁸ Christoph Brabec,⁵

Marcus Bär,^{3,7} Dirk M. Guldi,⁷ Maïssa K. S. Barr,² Julien Bachmann,^{2,9} Filip Bureš!^[WU1]

Figure S1. Photo of the research-scale sALD reactor.

Figure S2. UV/Vis spectroscopy measurement of 100 cycles of Sb₂Se₃ as-grown (red curve) and annealed at 300 °C for 5 min, N₂ (black curve) using bis-(tributylstannyl) selenide (**5**) as Se²⁻ source.

Figure S3. Raman spectra measured on Sb_2Se_3 coated glass slide (as-grown and annealed at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 5 min, N_2) using bis-(trimethylstannyl) selenide (**5**) as Se^{2-} source.

Figure S4. (a) EDX line scan along a $10\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ TiO_2 nanotubes (TNT) substrate coated with 50 cycles Sb_2Se_3 using bis-(trimethylstannyl) selenide (**5**) as Se^{2-} source and (b) corresponding SEM micrograph with scan path.

TBT2Se-Siw_[VK2]-hexane 001

RMS:760 pm, cov: 3.25%

TMT2Se-Siw-hexane[VK3] 2D.JPG

RMS:875 pm, cov: 13.75%

TMT2Se-Siw-CH2Cl2 001

RMS: 1.959 nm, cov: 14.5%

11%; 3.92 nm

TMT2Se-Siw-chlorobenzene

RMS: 2.4 nm, cov: 15.25%

Figure S5.

Figure S6. XPS core level spectra of 300 cycles Sb_2Se_3 as-grown and annealed (300 °C, 5 min, N_2) on Si wafer with native oxide: (a) C 1s, (b) Cl 2p, (c) Sn 3d and (d) Si 2p.

-- Figure --

Figure S7. Imaging ellipsometry map of a Si/SiO₂ wafer coated with 75 cycles Sb_2Se_3 . [WU4]